

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF FLAVONOIDS IN HORSETAIL (*EQUISETUM ARVENSE*)

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Relevance: Flavonoids, being an important group of plant secondary metabolites, play a key role in the physiological functioning of plants and have a wide range of biological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and cardioprotective effects. Horsetail (*Equisetum arvense*) is one of the plants traditionally used in folk medicine, known for its medicinal properties due, among other things, to the presence of flavonoids.

Purpose and objectives

The purpose of this study is to conduct a phytochemical analysis of the flavonoids contained in horsetails using modern extraction methods, chromatographic and spectroscopic analysis to determine the composition and concentration of flavonoids. The paper considers the main types of flavonoids, such as equisetin, quercetin, kaempferol, apigenin and their possible role in biological processes related to the effect on antioxidant activity and strengthening of vascular walls.

To preliminarily determine the presence of flavonoids, qualitative reactions were performed with ferric (III) chloride, a 10% alcoholic alkali solution, a 2% aqueous aluminum chloride solution, a basic lead acetate solution, and a Briant cyanidin reaction. The positive result of the reactions suggested the presence of flavonoids in the studied raw materials.

Extracts using solvents such as methanol, ethanol and acetone were used to extract flavonoids. Thin-layer chromatography (THC) methods were used to identify and quantify flavonoids. Two main spots should be visible on the chromatogram: with R_f about 0.57 and R_f about 0.5, having bright blue fluorescence in UV light at 254 nm or blue with violet fluorescence at 360 nm, as well as with R_f about 0.4, having blue with turquoise fluorescence in UV light at 254 nm or blue in UV light at 360 nm (flavone-5-glycosides). Other uncharacteristic spots are allowed. The chromatogram is sprayed with a 2% solution of aluminum chloride in 95% alcohol, placed in a drying cabinet for 1-2 minutes at 100-105 °C. After the appearance of the spots R_f about 0.57 and 0.5 do not change their color, the spot with R_f about 0.4 turns yellow in visible and UV light.

Result: The data obtained indicate the presence of a significant amount of flavonoids in horsetail extracts, among which equisetin and quercetin demonstrate the highest concentration and biological activity. According to research, the content of flavonoids in horsetails (*Equisetum arvense*) can range from 0.1% to 0.5% of the total weight of the plant in dry form. The chromatogram showed visible spots in UV light at 254 nm and 360 nm, and qualitative reactions were performed to identify the presence of flavanoids.

Conclusions: These results highlight the prospects of using horsetail as a source of flavonoids for the development of phytotherapeutic agents aimed at improving the condition of the cardiovascular system and reducing inflammation.